

A Study on “Measuring Job Satisfaction Level of Employees” With Reference to Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd

N. Veena, K. Jayanth

Associate Professor, Mother Theresa Institute of Management,
Palamaner, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Study has been showed in order to censoriously assess and observe the level of employees' satisfaction as well as the influences of dissatisfaction among the employees of Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd. The purpose of this study is also to perceive and examine the problems which create job dissatisfaction specifically among the punctilious superiors, and to find out the reasons which make them understand that they do not have a clear career path along working with Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd. The primary data for this study was compiled through questionnaire filled in on a one-to-one basis by 50 respondents from a representative sample of employees of Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd in chittoor district in the last quarter of 2017. The results have shown that Working atmosphere, Total Compensation, Development Chances and Training & Development are significant factor and these four are affecting Job Satisfaction and correlated with each other's. The study was faced by certain limitations and those limitations included time constraints and resources constraints, which limited this research to only Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd. According to a number of literatures studied, lack of job satisfaction is a serious problem in several organizations and job dissatisfaction has become a major hurdle in employees' productivity and firm's development. There are numbers of factors which can create job dissatisfaction among employees but in this study the very critical factors are discussed upon which Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd management should really work on.

Keyword: *Employees' Job Satisfaction; job security; motivation; Growth; Compensation*

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a multi-dimensional approach; it is made up of approach towards work conditions, pay, and relationship with co-workers, benefits, and performance evaluation system of the company etc. promotion, supervision, contingent rewards, nature of work, communication, and participation. Employee job satisfaction is one of the significant aspects of organizational effectiveness. Generally, it is an employee general attitude toward the job. Moreover, a job satisfaction is the extent to which a person is gratified or fulfilled by his or her work. The level of job satisfaction of the employees in the organization play vital role for the maintenance and hold of the knowledgeable employees in the organization. A satisfied worker tends to be fewer absent from his or her job, contribute for the benefit of the company and would like to stay in the organization. On the other hand, a dissatisfied employee has negative outlooks and prefers to remain absent too often, always remains unhappy with the supervisor, tries to leave the company once an opportunity is available, and remains in stress. The paper aims at assessing the job satisfaction status of employees and identifying the significant factors that influence the job satisfaction of the employees in Tirumala Milk Products (P) Ltd. The study also examines the relationships between job satisfaction and different demographic factors.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted in Tirumala milk products (Pvt. Ltd) for the purpose of fulfillment of the curriculum. The study is conducted on the topic "job satisfaction" because it is very important for an individual in an organization to show involvement

and commitment. The study is conducted with a hope that it may help in my studies in personnel management. There are three important dimensions to job satisfaction. First is an emotional response to a job situation. As such, it cannot be seen, it can only be inferred. Second job satisfaction is often determined by how well out comes are met or exceed expectations. Third job satisfaction represents several related attitudes Smith Kendall and Halin have suggested that there are five dimensions that represent the most important characteristics of a job about which people have affective responses

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the employees opinion about nature of working condition and pay.
- To find satisfaction of employees about statutory and non-statutory welfare measures provided to motivate employees.
- To identify the Employee opinion about Salary/Remuneration
- To identify the attitude of the general manager
- To identify the employees working condition

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Due to shortage of time constraint sample size is conferred to 50.
- Due to fear some employees are not co-operated me
- General manager of tirumala milk products Pvt. Ltd reduced my questioners due to avoid un necessary wastage of time

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

In the organizational study, job satisfaction occupies a dominant role in many theories and models of individual attitudes and behaviors. The concept of job satisfaction has been defined in many ways. However, the most-used definition of job satisfaction in organizational research is that of Locke (1976), who described job satisfaction as “an agreeable or optimistic emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences.” Syeyen and Van Wk (1999) mentioned that job satisfaction is a sense of desire as ensuing from a person’s insights of his or her work. Mwamwenda (1995) find a link between job satisfaction and productivity, commitment, fulfillment and continuance in a job situation. Job satisfaction is the sum of pleasure or contentment connected with a job (Dubrin, 1997). Job satisfaction is a result of employees’ perception of how well their job provides those things that are viewed as important (Luthans,

2002). In his study, Smither (1998) indicated that most people seem to have higher order needs, such as those involving self-actualization. It follows that only individuals who have high needs for fulfillment on the job are satisfied by having a job which provides the opportunities for such needs to be fulfilled (Hackman & Lawler, 1971).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this connection it is worth mentioning here that in order to collect the data on the prescribed closed-ended questionnaire, it was compelling need to stay and build up reputation with respondents. In order to get the questionnaire filled meeting with respondent was difficult. Therefore co-operation of reputed personalities of the departments was sought. Job was also difficult in the sense that respondents hesitated to cooperate with strangers due to privacy and bad conditions of law and order situation in tirumala milk products pvt. Questionnaire used is self-administered based on Likert scale format with a four point response scale. In this type of questionnaire the respondents were given four response choices. These options served as the quantification of the participant’s highly satisfactory, Satisfactory, Moderate, and Dissatisfactory on each question.

Data source	- Primary & Secondary Data
Research approach	- Interview
Research instrument	- Questionnaire
Method of contact	- Personal
Sample Size	- 50

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETION

Table 1 Respondents Opinion about the Working Condition

Opinion	No Of Respondents	Percentage
Very Good	14	28
Good	26	52
Average	8	16
Poor	1	2
Need Improvement	1	2
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s opinion about the working condition of the respondents)

Inference

It is noted from the above analysis that 28.0% of the respondents opined that working condition is very good, 52.0% of the respondents opined that working condition is good, 16.0% of the respondents opined that working condition is average and 2.0% of the respondents opined that working condition is poor and need improvement. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents opined that working condition is good.

Table2 Respondents Opinion Regarding Present pay

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	31	62
No	7	14
Can’t Say	12	24
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent opinion regarding present pay)

Inference

It is noted from the above analysis that 62.0% of the respondents are satisfied with pay, 14.0% of the respondents are not satisfied with pay and 24.0% of the respondents are unable to say any comments. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with pay.

Table3 Respondents Opinion about Promotional Opportunities

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage
Very Good	21	42
Good	21	42
Average	8	16
Poor	-	-
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s opinion about promotional opportunities)

Inference

It is identified from the above analysis that 42.0% of the respondents opined that company provide very good and good promotional offers and 16.0% of the respondents opined that the company provide promotional offers with average. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents opined that the company provide very good and good promotional offers.

Table 4 Respondents Satisfy Action on Training Programmes

Opinion	No Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	32	64
Not satisfied	18	36
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s satisfaction on training programmers)

Inference

It is identified from the above analysis that 64.0% of the respondents are satisfied with training programmers and remaining 36.0% of the respondents are not satisfied with training programmers. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with training programmers

Table 5 Respondents Satisfaction with the Statutory Welfare Schemes

Opinion	No Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	33	66
Not satisfied	17	34
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s satisfaction with the statutory welfare schemes)

Inference

It is identified from the above analysis that 66.0% of the respondents are satisfied with Statutory Welfare Schemes and remaining 34.0% of the respondents are not satisfied with Statutory Welfare Schemes. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with Statutory Welfare Schemes.

Table 6 Respondents Satisfaction on Level of Job Security

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage
Highly satisfactory	12	24
Satisfactory	17	34
Moderate	17	34
Dissatisfaction	2	4
Highly Dissatisfaction	2	4
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s satisfaction on level of job security)

Inference

It is noted from the above analysis that 24.0% of the respondents are highly satisfied with job security, 34.0% of the respondents are satisfied with job security, 34.0% of the respondents are moderately satisfied with job security and 4.0% of the respondents are dissatisfaction and highly dissatisfied with job security. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with job security.

Table 7 Respondents Satisfaction on Level of Target Related Incentives

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfactory	24	48
Neutral	19	38
Not Satisfactory	7	14
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s satisfaction on level of target related incentives)

Inference

It is observed from the above analysis that 48.0% of the respondents are satisfied with incentives, 38.0% of the respondents are neutrally satisfied with incentives and 14.0% of the respondents are not satisfied with incentives. It is concluded from the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with incentives.

Table 8 Respondents Opinion about Grievance Handling System

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	26	52
Not satisfied	24	48
Total	50	100

(The chart refers to respondent’s opinion about grievance handling system)

Inference

It is identified from the above analysis that 52.0% of the respondents are satisfied with Grievance handling system, 48.0% of the respondents are not satisfied with Grievance handling system. It is concluded from

the above analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with Grievance handling system.

FINDINGS

- It is evident from the analysis that maximum of the respondents are satisfied with pay (62).
- It is found from the study that most of the respondents are opined that the company provides very good and good promotional offers (52).
- It is found from the analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with training programmers (64).
- It is evident from the study that maximum of the respondents are satisfied with statutory welfare schemes (66).
- It is concluded from the analysis that most of the respondents are satisfied with the rest room facilities provided by the TMPL sugars.
- It is evident from the study that majority of the respondents are opined that they can easily communicate with superiors (64).
- It is found from the analysis that maximum of the respondents are satisfied with job security (34).
- It is concluded from the study that most of the respondents are satisfied with incentives (48).
- It is evident from the analysis that majority of the respondents are satisfied with grievance handling system (52).
- There is no significant relationship between age and opinion regarding working condition.

SUGGESTIONS:

- The company has to consider qualification for recruiting the employees for the job.
- The company has to increase that working environment and provide the employees with good quality food.
- The workers should co-ordinate with the co-workers at the same time superior should be liberal with their employees for better communication.
- The management should consider the suggestion of employees.
- The company should provide some training programmers and proper incentives for the target achieved by the employees.
- The company should provide good welfare facilities and rest room facilities to the employees.
- The management should provide good job security to the employees.

CONCLUSION:

According to a number of literatures which have been studied, lack of job satisfaction is a serious issue in various organizations and job dissatisfaction has become a main problem in employees' efficiency and firm development. It is the surveys conclude that in the Tirumala milk products private limited for knowing the job satisfaction level of employees the survey result all positive sign. The workers are fearing better satisfaction while working in Tirumala milk products private limited not only satisfying but also giving suggestions to the management and also showing good results at work place. Some percentage of the people are not satisfying with the organization has to take immediate action towards the dissatisfaction. The working conditions are well when compare with all other competitive organizations. Maintaining good relations with the employees will give good results for the company. Make more effect the relation between the employees as well as the superiors and subordinates. Training is also a matter to discuss. Each and every time it has to revise what type of training programs they are giving good results or not, it if not where is the problem creating. It is the time to conduct the study about all the aspects mentioned by the employees. Management decisions towards the employees will also causes the problem. So maintain better relations with the employees by the management.

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